

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Report of the First European Carbon Farming Summit

Deliverable 4.1

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

www.project-credible.eu

Document information

GRANT AGREEMENT N°	101112951
Project title	Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU
Project acronym	CREDIBLE
Project duration	3 years
Coordinators	SAE (Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL)
Related work packages(s)	WP4. Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU
Related task(s)	T4.1 EU Carbon Farming summits
Lead organisation	EIT Climate-KIC
Contributing partner(s)	CKIC, SAE, CREAM, COOP
Due date	30/06/2024
Submission date	04/07/2024
Dissemination level	PU

History

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR	DESCRIPTION	REVIEWED BY
1.0.	19/06/2024	Christiana Oragbade	First version	Daniel Zimmer
1.1.	26/06/2024	Daniel Zimmer	Second version (new Executive Summary, additional conclusions, compliance with template)	Tristano Bacchetti
1.2.	01/07/2024	Daniel Zimmer	Third version, with project summary and Appendices	Aleix Valls Juan Sagarna Tristano Bacchetti
1.3.	04/07/2024	Daniel Zimmer	Final version with recommendations from BOS	

Table of Contents

Document information.....	2
History	2
Table of Contents	3
Executive summary	4
Acronyms and abbreviations	5
Project Summary	5
The First Summit in Numbers.....	7
Summary of the plenary sessions	9
A mandate to achieve climate neutrality	9
Providing technical and financial support to scale up carbon farming	10
Adopting a best-fit methodology	11
It's not only about carbon: the importance of a holistic approach and of co-benefits	12
Outcomes of the Focus Group Breakout Sessions (BOS)	12
BOS1: Helping farmers to identify the most suitable carbon farming practices.....	13
BOS2: How to measure the economic returns linked to the co-benefits of increasing soil organic matter.....	14
BOS3: Carbon farming that safeguards food security and biodiversity	15
BOS4: Developing a fit-for-region approach to carbon farming.....	16
BOS5: Harmonisation of the Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV) protocols of carbon farming systems.....	17
BOS6: Innovations in proximal sensing and digitalization for carbon farming purposes	18
BOS7: Earth Observation applications for monitoring carbon removals.....	19
BOS8: Using data from long-term monitoring sites in the context of carbon farming	21
BOS9: Minimum requirements to ensure carbon farming delivers sustainability benefits	22
BOS10: Europe-wide vs regional certification frameworks: pros and cons	24
BOS11: An effective policy mix for an environment conducive to carbon farming	25
Communications, dissemination and visibility	28
Press Release & On-Site Comms	29
Social Media	30
Lessons learned	31
Appendices.....	34
Appendix 1: 1st Carbon Farming Summit digital agenda	34
Appendix 2: Examples of posters during the Summit	36

Executive summary

The first European Carbon Farming Summit was organised in Valencia (Spain) from 5-7 March 2024 as part of the EU-funded project Credible: *Building momentum and trust to achieve credible carbon farming in the EU* (GA-101112951; HE topic call HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06).

The summit gathered 600+ participants, including 265 on site and 358 on-line from around 20 countries. It was organised around a mix of plenary sessions and breakout sessions (BOS) organised by 11 focus groups (FG) of the Credible project i.e.

- FG 1.1. Helping farmers to identify the most suitable carbon farming practices
- FG 1.2. How to measure the economic returns linked to the co-benefits of increasing soil organic matter
- FG 1.3. Carbon farming that safeguards food security and biodiversity
- FG 1.4. Developing a fit-for-region approach to carbon farming
- FG 2.1. Harmonisation of the Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV) protocols of carbon farming systems
- FG 2.2. Innovations in proximal sensing and digitalization for carbon farming purposes
- FG 2.3. Earth Observation applications for monitoring carbon removals
- FG 2.4. Using data from long-term monitoring sites in the context of carbon farming
- FG 3.1. Minimum requirements to ensure carbon farming delivers sustainability benefits
- FG 3.2. Europe-wide vs regional certification frameworks: pros and cons
- FG 3.3. An effective policy mix for an environment conducive to carbon farming

DG Clima of the EU Commission opened and actively contributed to the Summit. Credible indeed complements the work of its Expert Group guiding the development of the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), which general directions have been adopted by the EU in February 2024.

The plenary sessions opened the discussions and comprised keynote lectures aiming to set the stage and inspire participants as well introductory presentations of the topics to be addressed as resulting from the work of the FGs of the project. The core of the discussion occurred in workshops organised and moderated by the 11 FGs.

Overall, this first Summit was a success: participation was more than initially expected, motivation of the participants for such a Summit was high, contribution and insights provided were of high quality. It was also recognized that the work produced by the various FGs (and related breakout sessions) complements well the work of the Expert Group of the CRCF of DG Clima. It also highlighted a shared view of most participants: carbon farming is more than an approach to store carbon in agricultural soils, it is -and needs to be- a tool to help the transformation of agriculture toward a more agroecological approach.

Acronyms and abbreviations

BOS	Breakout Session
CRCF	Carbon Removal Certification Framework
FG	Focus Group
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IoT	Internet of Things
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LTM	Long Term Monitoring
MRV	Monitoring Reporting and Verification
SOC	Soil Organic Content
SOM	Soil Organic Matter
VCM	Voluntary Carbon Market

Project Summary

Carbon Farming, a whole farm approach to optimizing carbon capture in agricultural soils is gaining traction globally. The Credible project aims to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming methods (practices, monitoring, certification) in the European Union, by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders, which promote transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardisation in soil carbon accounting. In Credible, transparent, open access, multi-actor dialogues will be orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits (2024-2026), which will present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder community to build trust and co-create solutions (Figure 1).

The European Carbon Farming Summits aim to become a platform for stakeholders to network and discuss carbon farming, build consensus and progressively create a Europe-wide community of practice on carbon farming. It is anticipated that the 3 summits will grow every year to the point that they would attract further funding for long term sustainability. The first summit aimed to be open to the professionals involved in supporting the development of carbon farming mechanisms, from practices to certification. The second one will be truly multi-stakeholder and be open to a large array of participants including farmers, NGOs, and private sector. The last summit will be used to mobilise in addition policy and decision makers and to derive a series of post-project priority actions that will be forwarded (and possibly endorsed) by the Soil Mission and the European Commission.

Figure 1: Timeline for the three summits during Credible project implementation

Overall, through Credible activities, four specific objectives (SO) will be achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming.

Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

Table 1 - CREDIBLE's work package structure.

WP #	WP name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 2 - CREDIBLE's consortium composition.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE

Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH	UFZ	DE
Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES
Baltic sea action group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
BioEconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Holding BV	CKIC	NL
University of Helsinki	UH	FI
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

The First Summit in Numbers

The first European Carbon Farming Summit convened in Valencia, Spain, on 5-7 March 2024, with over 600 scientists, researchers, policy makers, land practitioners and enthusiasts dedicated to carbon farming. With a blend of in-person and virtual participation, the event highlighted the European community's strong commitment to scaling the potential of carbon farming. The framing and focus of the first Summit were articulated around the three areas outlined in the Credible project description (Fig. 2) i.e. carbon farming practices, MRV and certification.

Figure 2: The three main areas of CREDIBLE project and of the summit

In each of these areas, a series of keynote addresses, open plenary discussions and breakout groups were organised where different topics were dynamically discussed in breakout sessions, poster presentations and pitches from summit participants. Some key facts about the first summit include:

- 600+ in-person and online participants;
- 6 keynote speeches by experts and policy makers from the European Commission, Joint Research Council (JRC), Agrosolutions, Fall Line Capital, and Commonland;
- 11 breakout sessions;
- 98 submitted contributions from external experts from more than 23 countries;
- 50+ pitches and 40+ poster presentations from Summit participants.

In-person attendance was roughly 170% higher than anticipated due to high demand. With an initial objective of ~150 in-person guests including keynote speakers, focus group members and representatives of the Credible project consortium, approximately 265 persons attended the summit in-person, while 358 joined online. Participation by stakeholder type was mixed with high attendance of consultancy groups involved in carbon MRV and certification and of academia. While some major companies were present, the vast majority of industry participants were from micro, small or medium enterprises (MSMEs) offering a product or service related to agriculture, forestry or related industries¹.

Figure 3: Participants during one of the poster presentation sessions

¹ This distribution is approximative, as many participants registered without indicating their affiliation. This may be because they were attending as private individuals, as independents (e.g. consultants, self-employed), farmers or foresters.

Participation by country was not precisely tracked, but by using the company location and registration e-mail accounts as proxies, more than 17 countries were represented, with Spain, Italy and Germany having the highest in-person participation. There was also in-person participation from people from Ukraine, Romania, Slovakia, Latvia and Portugal, respectively, as well as from outside Europe, including Canada, the USA, and Latin America & Caribbean (representatives of the Inter-American Development Bank), respectively.

Summary of the plenary sessions

The Summit emphasised the importance of considering the unique conditions, ecosystems, and socio-economic factors of different regions across Europe while harnessing the strengths of collaboration and innovation to trigger the implementation of credible carbon farming in Europe. The keynote speakers presented an overview of the current context and challenges facing Europe as well as the opportunities to align carbon farming with other measures to improve Europe's land-based ecosystems. Recordings of the plenary sessions as well as the presentations are made available on the website of the Summit:

www.carbonfarmingsummit.eu/previous_edition.

A mandate to achieve climate neutrality

The summit highlighted the necessity of a harmonised approach to carbon credit certification across Europe. Although globally the voluntary carbon market (VCM) size was around 2-billion-dollars in 2021, with increasing financial flows and demand, several recent studies and media reports on the low quality of carbon credits and their exaggerated additionality claims have left the VCM open to criticism². This has resulted in a fall in trust among the general public and key stakeholders in carbon markets as part of the solution to tackling the climate crisis.

Christian Holzleitner from the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action opened the summit by presenting how the European Union's adopted Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) provides measures to overcome the challenges facing Europe's VCM, by improving quality, cost-efficiency and harmonisation at the EU-level, providing more robust guidelines for certification and developing an MRV framework which would drive down costs and improve the quality of carbon credits.

² See for example: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2023/sep/19/do-carbon-credit-reduce-emissions-greenhouse-gases>

Figure 5: Christian Holzleitner from the European Commission during the Summit Opening

The CRCF aims to address the growing significance of carbon management and removals as a component of Europe's strategy to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 alongside bioeconomy and clean energy, as well as other EU financial and policy mechanisms such as the Common Agricultural Policy and the Soil and Forest Monitoring Laws. It aims to support an increased uptake and roll-out of carbon farming in the EU.

Providing technical and financial support to scale up carbon farming

Farmers, land managers and practitioners are central to the successful scaling up of carbon farming in Europe. However, the diversity and complexity of the methodological bases behind each public or private certification scheme, along with costly and complex MRV frameworks and limited affordable farmer advisory services, among other factors, have created barriers for them to leverage sufficient capital to transition to or scale up carbon farming.

To overcome this barrier, complementary financing mechanisms and incentives need to be explored. Valeria Forlin from DG Clima presented the top-line objectives of the CRCF. She stressed that a unified and standardised approach is essential to level the playing field and reduce operating and monitoring costs. Such a harmonised approach would facilitate easier comparison and evaluation of carbon credits, encouraging greater participation in carbon trading and investment. This in turn would lead to increased farmer advisory support services, more private initiatives, additional public funding and greater credibility and trust in carbon markets and climate neutrality claims.

Figure 6: Valeria Forlin from the European Commission

Edouard Lanckriet from Agrosolutions pointed to the several financing mechanisms which already exist in the agri-food sector, such as public subsidies, carbon credits, and premiums paid by companies committed to their Science-Based Targets (SBTs). However, to scale carbon farming in agriculture, clear and harmonized rules are needed, so that agricultural business models can work with multiple, complementary, financial flows to reduce the financial burden and business operating risks generally placed on farmers in transitioning to carbon farming.

Adopting a best-fit methodology

Carbon farming will require the development of MRV frameworks which are robust and accurate but effective at the right scale, i.e., fit for purpose. In his presentation, Panos Panagos highlighted key results from the JRC's studies in estimating carbon trends and developing new methods for MRV using geospatial data across multiple observation points in Europe combined with data collected at the parcel level. He highlighted that there are still uncertainties due to biophysical variations, the type of carbon farming practices and the changing fluxes within agricultural carbon stocks. He stressed the importance of collaboration with the soil research community and Soil Mission projects such as Credible, to improve scientific knowledge and data-driven approaches to carbon farming which account for local contexts and conditions.

Edouard Lanckriet reminded the participants that carbon farming should focus on creating confidence among agri-food stakeholders, including land managers and practitioners, and responding to the reality to the ground. He described the importance of a framework for the agricultural system which considers non-permanent biogenically stored carbon in agriculture, arguing that there needs to develop appropriate approaches to measure carbon within the agricultural system, going beyond permanent carbon stocks as the sole unit of measurement. This, he argued, would significantly reduce the risk of double-counting of

climate claims from agro-industry and provide greater provision of carbon finance for farmers.

It's not only about carbon: the importance of a holistic approach and of co-benefits

Many of the keynote speakers highlighted that carbon farming is not only about carbon; rather, carbon farming should be seen as a measure to provide benefits to the whole ecological system, and to land managers, in the form of financial returns and healthier soils. Giulia Stellari from Fall Line Capital maintained that it is important to identify and scale the land use practices which provide not only benefits to soil carbon, but to biodiversity, water and other soil elements.

Willem Ferwerda from Commonland argued that carbon farming is not a panacea for achieving climate neutrality; it is a core component of the wider regeneration of landscapes and the transformation of how land is used and managed, but this can only happen if the benefits for farmers, communities, and ecology are prioritised.

He highlighted the challenges of uniting people towards a holistic landscape restoration approach and in building trust among stakeholders and local communities. The focus should not be on returns on investment, but on restoring ecological functionality. Carbon finance, such as carbon credits, should therefore be seen as complementary financing within the broader goal to accelerate Europe's landscape restoration and ecological functionality, and should be harnessed to that effect.

Outcomes of the Focus Group Breakout Sessions (BOS)

During the Summit, the Credible project's 11 Focus Groups built on the plenary presentations through deliberations and an open Q&A session during their respective panel discussions and explored issues within their respective focus area in more detail during their breakout sessions (BOSs), as well as identify new questions worth exploring. Summit participants were invited to attend these parallel sessions and enrich the conversation with their own research findings, data or experiences, many in the form of poster presentations or "pitches". Below is a short summary of the outcomes of these discussions, following the title of the Breakout Session (BOS) during the Summit.

A full report on the outcomes of the public consultations (incl. the Summit sessions) for each focus area is available via the Credible Project website: <https://www.project-credible.eu/consultations>.

BOS1: Helping farmers to identify the most suitable carbon farming practices

Organisers: Julio Román and Miguel Angel Repullo, European Conservation Agriculture Federation

Sparse scientific literature and field-level complexities are hindering the collection of robust evidence on which practices can have the highest impact in terms of climate mitigation. However, based on the experience of pioneer farmers, it should be possible to identify best options for carbon removal and emission reduction in each pedoclimatic context. Furthermore, to succeed in scaling up beneficial practices, it is fundamental to identify impactful ways to engage and communicate to the primary sector.

During the first Summit, participants contributed towards building scientific consensus on which practices should be prioritized in the EU according to land uses. Discussions revolved around critical questions such as “What are the key factors to consider in defining a practice as Carbon Farming?”, “What are the main barriers to engage farmers in adopting innovative techniques on Carbon Farming? How can these barriers be broken?”, and “What are the strategies for the successful spread of carbon farming practices?” Participants provided insights and comments on the barriers and strategies for scaling Carbon Farming, while the invited pitch presenters enriched the conversation with data and information from their own respective works.

The main recommendations coming out of this Session were as follows:

About **practices and indicators**:

- It is important to define indicators for considering a practice as part of carbon farming. These indicators must always be measurable, have a demonstrable scientific basis and be quantifiable.
- Carbon farming practices should be easily adaptable to different pedoclimatic regions and should take a holistic view, considering not only the rate of carbon sequestration and emission reduction but also the ecosystem services provided by these practices.
- There is a need to advise farmers and land users to continue applying carbon farming if the results are not desirable.

About **Barriers** to adopting the practices:

- There is a lack of cooperation and knowledge of how to apply the practices on the ground, which is why not only the practices should be promoted, but also ongoing advice.
- Access to technology is often lacking.
- Economic barriers, low demand for C credits and the cost of the transition are also important.

On **how to spread** the integration of carbon farming practices in Europe:

- Transferring knowledge through examples, the creation of training centres is necessary.
- Practices need to be credible and transparent, showing the difficulties of implementing the practices and giving clear advice on what the real carbon sequestration and emission reduction potential is.

- Scalability of practices and development of regional definitions of Carbon Farming Practices need to be ensured.
- Operational and comprehensible certification and smart subsidy programs would encourage farmers to adopt carbon farming practices.

Figure 7: Participants discussing during one of the breakout sessions

BOS2: How to measure the economic returns linked to the co-benefits of increasing soil organic matter

Organiser: Andrea Ferrarini, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Italy

For every ton of carbon sequestered in the soil there is almost 2 tons of soil organic matter (SOM) that are built-up. SOM supports farm profitability through various co-benefits, including storing water, replacing fertilisers, increasing soil workability and reducing fuel consumption. It is believed that carbon farming is a great opportunity to bring the primary sector to realise the potential economic impact of these co-benefits.

During the first Summit, participants contributed towards crafting a blueprint for a common accounting approach, speaking the language of carbon farmers and going beyond the economic value of carbon credits. The objective was to agree on the simplest model/equations available to calculate monetary values of SOC sequestration and SOM co-benefits. The agronomic benefits considered were the soil function and fertility benefits of SOM (increased nutrient cycling measured as nutrients replacement value, plant-available water-holding capacity measured as estimated productivity improvement, and improved aggregate stability measured as reduced fuel consumption for tillage).

BOS3: Carbon farming that safeguards food security and biodiversity

Organiser: Pilar Andrés Pastor, Ecological and Forestry Applications Research Centre (CREAF), Spain

Focusing on soil carbon sequestration might cause unintended consequences, and there is a lively debate on its dynamic interactions with biodiversity and food security. During the Summit this group explored these nuanced relationships and allowed participants to contribute to evidence-based insights such as: (a) synergies/antagonisms that should be taken into account when planning for carbon farming; (b) which organisations/initiatives should be engaged when trying to address these issues? (c) how can we articulate a conversation that is visible and impactful?

The aim of the discussions was to collect opinions and knowledge on how to avoid the threat that carbon farming might impose on food production and biodiversity, while on the contrary supporting positive synergies. Some interesting reflections which emerged during the discussions include scientific and technical issues, markets and economic factors, and capacity building and farmers' perceptions.

The main conclusions and recommendations of this BOS were as follows:

- Neither sequestered carbon nor crop yield alone are appropriate indicators of a successful C farming strategy: increasing farm profitability and resilience is what can stimulate farmers to engage in C farming.
- Wide-range EU protocols are not useful in supporting agricultural conversion. Tailoring C farming practices at the lowest possible local scale in terms of soil and climate characteristics is vital.
- Dry regions should be prioritized to increase their resilience to climate change and to take profit of their high capacity for C sequestration in their carbon depleted soils.
- Given the great European (social, economic and environmental) heterogeneity, we should better pay for selected practices per region, and the results in C terms should be continuously monitored.
- Rewards for C sequestration must be conditioned to the “no-harm” principle applied to environmental services, including biodiversity.
- Rewards and incentives should be proportional to farmers' efforts to sequester carbon and should include payment for additional effort in improving environmental services (including biodiversity).
- Fostering agroecology and other holistic approaches to agricultural production can guarantee large-scale production of basic grains and cereals at affordable prices and crop diversification while cooperating to C sequestration.
- Recovering integrated traditional systems, with agriculture embedded within natural areas, could increase the available area for crop production while reducing wildfire risk and increasing biodiversity.

- Facilitate interaction between conventional farmers and farmers engaged in the transition. Farmers follow the path of other successful farmers. Do not forget farmers that have no access to information.
- Verify that Member States design and implement high-quality AKISs to support farmers in the transition. Facilitate monitoring by public organisms at fair price: they are operating with (often European) public resources.

BOS4: Developing a fit-for-region approach to carbon farming

Organisers: Ján Hegyi, Bioeconomy Cluster, Slovakia, and Kaj Granholm, Baltic Sea Action Group, Finland

One option is that carbon farming should be seen as a transformation tool, enabling the transition toward regenerative food and fibre systems and restored landscapes. It could be most impactful when based on methodologies and schemes that are meaningful at the regional level, capable of inspiring rural communities in bringing life back to the soil. The term fit-for-region carbon farming is used to express this idea.

The session featured presentations, two rounds of group discussions and consolidation of the session findings, as follows:

Group 1: Establishing regional need and vision

Explore how multi-stakeholder approaches can help different EU regions to effectively implement the EU Carbon Farming Framework, meet the Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria, and to minimize the burden for farmers.

Group 2: Building regional carbon farming schemes through Living Labs

To discuss and identify the potential of Living Labs to help with the establishment of regional carbon farming schemes - challenges, opportunities and economic aspects.

Group 3: Gearing up regional initiatives to serve EU policy development

To discuss the value of developing and shaping EU policy based on a better understanding of the regional context and local implementation capacity, what the regions and regional initiatives should do to serve as credible reference points for EU policy, and what paths for cooperation could be utilized for these aims.

Group 4: Producing economic and ecosystem goods through public-private partnership

To discuss private carbon farming reward schemes, their ability to support both primary production, ecosystem services and systemic transition, and the challenges and opportunities considering public and private expectations.

The main conclusions and recommendations of this BOS were as follows:

- Strong central (EU/national) public sector role with complementary local/regional adaptation and dimension is key to success. Public administration must also retain overall responsibility and sufficient resourcing for agricultural advisory services needed to guide farmers in the transition.
- All carbon farming schemes of course need to consider regional aspects which are very specific for each region. This could be solvable via building regional carbon farming schemes through Living Labs because they could engage all stakeholders.
- The main purpose of carbon farming schemes should be to complement the public funding to support carbon farming transition and create value added for all stakeholders, through e.g. increasing sustainability at farm level and paying for ecosystem services that are not recognized or valued today.
- Attention to data quality and management are keys to viable and scalable schemes.

BOS5: Harmonisation of the Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV) protocols of carbon farming systems

Organiser: Maria Fantappiè, CREA, Italy

A robust system for carbon farming MRV is required to monitor policies and to attract investments in this field. Private companies use different approaches in terms of modelling, analytical or estimation methods, and sampling protocols. Furthermore, these data are usually not accounted for in the national reporting, due to the lack of data quality & standardisation, of data harmonisation and of good practices for data sharing. An EU-wide harmonisation is therefore needed with JRC-LUCAS soil monitoring as the central reference.

This session gave an opportunity to present experiences on the topic of transnational data harmonisation options, focusing on three main themes connected in the standardisation and harmonisation efforts related to MRV: 1) harmonising soil analysis: standards and protocols; 2) enabling soil data sharing; and 3) producing baselines – needs and challenges.

The main conclusions and recommendations from this BOS were the following:

1. The government structure of the EU regulated market should include the requirement to comply with quality criteria for laboratories and VCM companies (e.g. to participate in interlaboratory calibration and to adopt standard methods and procedures; SOC measurements should always be accompanied by uncertainty levels). A clear list of minimum quality standards should be published.
2. The analytical standards adopted should be declared in the metadata and clear guidance should be given on the metadata standard to be applied, to facilitate the publication of all the information needed for interoperability of the data produced.

3. Reference analytical standards and standard sampling protocols to be applied should be defined, and harmonisation functions towards the reference standard should be defined.
4. The data should be in the same format to be easily shareable. Therefore, tools should be created and made available for standard data sharing.
5. To incentivize private companies to share their data, the effort of data collection should in large part be subsidised with the support of the EU. The farmer should have the ability to request a subsidy for data collection (such as soil sampling) and hire a company to perform the sampling and lab analysis.
6. To ensure the respect of privacy, the data shared should be maps which show aggregated data (e.g. at country level). However, the model needs data at a fine spatial scale in order to have accurate estimations of carbon sequestration in the soil.
7. Carbon removals and emission reductions MRV systems have different scopes, different approaches to baselines. Furthermore, the term baseline is used both for baseline practices (Business As Usual) and for the baseline soil carbon content. This double use creates confusion.
8. To overcome the challenge of accounting for the additionality, we suggest defining reference mean soil organic carbon values for each EU pedoclimatic zone, or even at finer scales, in the scenario of Business as Usual at current climatic conditions. These mean baseline SOC values could enable valorising those farmers who are already above the mean value.
9. The maintenance of carbon storage should be rewarded. But to do this, it is required to know the standard storage performance of the region.

BOS6: Innovations in proximal sensing and digitalization for carbon farming purposes

Organisers: Paulina Rajewicz and Jon Atherton, University of Helsinki, Finland

The rapid and continual development of digital technologies presents a variety of opportunities for carbon farming, but it also introduces substantial challenges. In the context of carbon farming, the use of available digital technologies, including electronic databases and geographic information systems, proximal sensing, artificial intelligence, and machine learning, and of electronic maps should be promoted to decrease the costs of establishing baselines and of monitoring carbon removal activities. Consequently, incorporating and connecting diverse digital technologies into cohesive MRV systems, constitutes a core element of carbon certification strategy.

The group discussed perspectives and scenarios for the use of diverse technologies for the purposes of carbon farming implementation, monitoring, evaluation and, finally, certification of carbon removal actions. Conversations were centred around three main themes related to MRV: 1) proximal sensing (standardisation of approaches; future role in MRV); 2) digitalisation (current state across Europe; existing digital resources; data exchange from farm to national level); and 3) the acceptance and transformative capacity, i.e., “social aspects” of these technologies (co-evolving innovations; guidelines on new technologies; communication). The invited pitchers in this group shared their expertise and experiences in, among others, IoT and AI in carbon monitoring, data- and science-based analytics for scalable carbon markets, and proximal sensing tools.

In summary, the BOS recommended:

- To propose a clear definition of proximal sensing in carbon farming to ensure consistency and comparability across initiatives.
- To develop a roadmap for the use of proximal sensing in MRV systems, which considers regionality, transparency, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness.
- To utilise existing digital data resources alongside new (e.g., proximal sensing) data in MRV systems.
- To provide user-friendly guidelines for farmers to implement proximal sensing and digital solutions, considering regional variations in farmers’ technology acceptance and transformative capacity.
- To design regional support networks, including local test sites and “farm lighthouses”, that would address barriers to technology acceptance, increase transformative capacity, and facilitate effective communication between farmers

BOS7: Earth Observation applications for monitoring carbon removals

Organisers: Monica Miguel-Lago and Michelle Hermes, European Association of Remote Sensing Companies (EARSC)

In the context of the European Green Deal and the Zero pollution Action Plan for 2050, the use of digital solutions is becoming increasingly important to meet the European Union's climate targets. More specifically, remote sensing technologies have some advantages, such as a large spatial coverage, allowing a continuous and global view of the Earth's parameters. By combining satellite data with measurements from ground-based instruments and the use of technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, it is possible to have a wide range of applications and services. Examples are the identification of the best geographical sites for establishing carbon farming practices, monitoring seasonal productivity and ongoing sequestration actions, helping to estimate ground biomass and supporting the evaluation of sequestered carbon volume, etc.

With its accuracy and scope, satellite information, such as data coming from the European flagship programme Copernicus and private missions, was recognized as a crucial tool to support the MRV of soil carbon fluxes. In particular, it could quantify above-ground biomass and estimate carbon sequestration when coupled/calibrated with in-situ field measurements. This session collected and shared technical evidence on the role of Earth Observation (EO) applications in supporting the implementation of the new carbon removals policy approach and portfolio development. Our goal was to capture the current opportunities and limitations on how EO can support Carbon removals.

The main conclusions and recommendations of this BOS were the following.

- Earth Observation (EO) facilitates data supply and comparison of methodologies. Satellite-derived data and services show promise in mapping and evaluating carbon farming but require further research and development, testing, and validation along with in-situ and ground truth data, in line with user needs. While the growth of carbon markets faces uncertainties, the demand for EO technology for carbon monitoring will continue, especially with the need for transparency and integrity in Voluntary Carbon Markets. Despite the existence of numerous methodologies, the lack of comprehensive operational standards that clearly define workflow and data needs in each process makes it difficult for EO service providers to enter the MRV market. Harmonising and standardising MRV methodologies for carbon farming is crucial for providing coherent solutions across different contexts, supported by real case scenarios and ongoing EU-level projects.
- Combining soil sampling with EO data in digital soil mapping models offers a promising approach for accurately measuring soil organic carbon content in the top layer of agricultural lands. Additionally, integrating EO data into ecosystem and biomass models enables the assessment of changes in soil organic carbon stocks through a carbon budget approach. These hybrid methodologies allow for highly precise estimates at the field or farm level, offering a more efficient alternative to traditional, expensive, and time-consuming methods. Satellites are also indispensable for quickly assessing forested areas, and recent studies demonstrate that the accuracy of available models for estimating key parameters is continually improving. Earth observation (EO) could serve as a valuable tool for monitoring forests worldwide.
- Definitions of terminology such as baseline, carbon removal, carbon sequestration, carbon farming, carbon storage in products, the durability of removal, and permanent carbon storage should be clearly defined to better understand and implement the regulation. Embracing a multi-actor approach involving a wide range of stakeholders and establishing a platform for sharing input data and testing environments for future EU-wide MRV tools is essential for the implementation of the CRCF. Dedicated funding and resources should be considered to create such a platform for data harmonisation and exchange. Collaboration and communication among stakeholders, both private and public, that are involved in carbon farming activities,

and more importantly farmers, producers and growers, are crucial for realising the full potential of these initiatives and ensuring successful implementation.

- Engaging with policy and legal experts to address data governance and ownership, while establishing clear regulations and standards, is essential for ensuring the success of integrating EO for MRV of CF. Similarly, the private sector's potential to accelerate the carbon market is underestimated, hindered by the absence of a harmonised standardisation framework. Without recognized "Carbon standards" and adequate incentives for stakeholders, progress remains slow despite social and political pressure for change.

BOS8: Using data from long-term monitoring sites in the context of carbon farming

Organisers: Tommy D'Hose and Hui Xu, ILVO, Belgium

Robust MRV is essential to ensure that carbon removals have environmental integrity and are real, additional, measurable, permanent, and avoid carbon leakage and double counting. While effective MRV is essential, it also poses a major challenge as it can be expensive to accurately measure and validate the GHG impact of carbon farming, resulting in a trade-off between MRV accuracy and cost. High MRV costs (financial or time) can act as a significant barrier to farmers voluntarily implementing carbon farming actions or to administrators establishing policies. Monitoring can be achieved by direct measurement, modelling, or a combined approach. For carbon farming to achieve its goal, measurements and models that are being used in the MRV system must be sufficiently reliable.

Therefore, the MRV system should be able to make use of, among others, controlled field experiments on research stations and pilot farms to understand the impact of carbon farming practices on soil carbon and the necessary experimental data and metadata to calibrate and validate carbon models. Several initiatives were already launched to group existing long-term monitoring sites (LTM) and to compile all available data. However, up till now, information remained scattered or incomplete to be of use for the calibration/validation of carbon models.

During the summit this group learned about participants' experiences as data users and/or providers. Discussions helped to elaborate on three major aspects: 1) the potential role of LTMs in MRV; 2) identifying the major challenges and barriers to effective use of LTMs data; and 3) potential solutions and recommendations, with the aim of developing a set of guidelines and considerations on how to make both experimental and metadata of long-term monitoring sites findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) in regional carbon farming schemes.

The main conclusions and recommendations from this BOS were the following.

- LTMs are crucial for assessing the long-term impacts of carbon farming practices and could serve as a test bed for the calibration and validation of SOC models. Besides,

they could facilitate the digitalisation of carbon farming practices, such as calibrating new sensors or providing ground truth data to support remote sensing research and development which are essential for modern, precise, and efficient agricultural monitoring. LTMs could therefore form vital components of national and international MRV platforms for SOC change.

- Among the challenges to the effective use of LTM data, three main categories were identified: (i) the lack of comprehensive coverage across different (new) management practices, land use types, climatic zones, and soil types in the existing LTMs, (ii) the FAIRness of the available (meta)data and (iii) technical challenges for both data users and providers such as GDPR and required skills for data management.
- To tackle the lack of representativeness of the existing LTMs, efforts should be made to start new LTMs in under-represented regions and to maximise the use of the Living Labs and Lighthouses which are initiated by the EU Soil Mission and could enhance the temporal and spatial resolution of LTMs and also serve as a platform for testing new management techniques and innovations in real-world settings.
- To increase the FAIRness of the available (meta)data, the focus should be placed on standardisation and harmonisation by e.g., adopting a fixed vocabulary and ensuring that datasets are published in quality-controlled data resources, such as community data repositories, to maintain high data quality and facilitate findability by both humans and computers. Besides, efforts should be made to make scientific research, including publications, data, physical samples, and software, as open access as possible to facilitate wider sharing
- Investments in sophisticated (meta)data management tools and training to assist LTMs owners in efficiently collecting, organising, storing, and managing data, thereby enhancing the overall quality and utility of the data collected, could help overcome the technical challenges. Finally, the publication of data papers should be encouraged and valorised to reward the efforts made by the LTMs owners.

BOS9: Minimum requirements to ensure carbon farming delivers sustainability benefits

Organisers: Hugh McDonald, Aron Scheidt and Julia Pazmino, Ecologic, Germany

Carbon farming actions impact not just climate mitigation, but also numerous other societal objectives (e.g. biodiversity, water quality and quantity, soil health and quality). Certification of carbon farming must promote sustainability to ensure that we can address multiple societal challenges simultaneously and to maximise benefits for different stakeholders. There is not yet a consensus approach for ensuring sustainability through carbon farming. The proposed EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework Regulation (CRCF) establishes four QU.A.L.ITY criteria for certification, one of which is sustainability; however, it is not yet determined how this will be operationalised. Existing voluntary carbon markets and public

funding mechanisms promote sustainability through carbon farming to differing degrees and in different ways.

This session sought input related to minimum requirements to ensure carbon farming delivered sustainability benefits. Four research questions were discussed with participants during the Summit: 1) which sustainability objectives need to be included and defined as part of EU Carbon Removals Certification Framework? 2) which approach should the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework implement to ensure sustainability benefits for carbon farming activities? And how can this approach become legally binding? 3) what are the challenges of delivering sustainability objectives through carbon farming certification (e.g. transaction costs, risk to upscaling, monitoring) - and how can these be managed? 4) how could activity-based sustainability requirements look like? At which level should activities be defined (farm activity, land-use typology)?

The main conclusions and recommendations from this BOS were the following:

- Sustainability standards are essential to correct and create trusted carbon markets raising new funds for the transition of the agricultural sector towards resilient and sustain-able business models.
- Carbon removal certification is a tool to support the transition towards economically, ecologically, and socially sustainable agricultural systems.
- Ecosystem services are highly interwoven and need to be recognized, quantified and rewarded. They are not a co-benefit of carbon removals but a core benefit to be considered as part of carbon removal solutions.
- We identified seven approaches to implement sustainability standards into a carbon removal certification framework.
- The integration and monitoring of sustainability standards needs to be reflected in higher value carbon credits and subsequent payments.
- The isolation of climate services carries the risk of reducing the value of climate-friendly agricultural measure while neglecting or even damaging other ecosystem services.

Figure 4: participants during a breakout session

BOS10: Europe-wide vs regional certification frameworks: pros and cons

Organisers: Clara DIEBOLT, and Claudine FOUCHEROT, Atlantic Agricultural Chamber of Commerce (AC3A), from the Regional Chamber of Agriculture of Normandy (CRAN)

A centralised European carbon farming certification framework can provide greater clarity for funders, reduce transaction costs and ensure the same level of requirements for everyone. Conversely, a decentralised approach can be better tailored to local circumstances and easier to use for local operators.

This session focused on sharing experiences from stakeholders involved in international, national, and local certification frameworks to reveal the strengths and weaknesses of the different scales, from single farms to nations, and predict potential interactions of overlapping schemes at different levels. The objective was to capture a potential pathway to the development of a harmonised multi-scheme certification framework that could support the deployment of nature-based solutions across the EU. The session organised a panel discussion during which the panellists addressed the following questions: 1) what could be the added value of the European certification framework? 2) will there be room for existing frameworks and in what form? What are the challenges to ensure the European framework fits in well with existing frameworks? 3) under what conditions will the European framework be operational on the ground and adaptable to local issues? 4) in a nutshell, what would be the key success factors for a European framework that is well combined with other scales and existing standards? A broader discussion among all participants ensued on the pros and cons of methodology development and validation for four different governance levels (scenarios).

The main conclusions and recommendations of this BOS were the following:

- European Carbon Certification is awaited to bring trust to fund carbon farming projects.
- Providing visibility and trust through a single register are important expectations of funders and projects developers.
- Certification Standards exist only in a few countries and international standards are not widely operating in the EU. Thus, CRCF will offer new fundings opportunities for carbon farming in many countries.
- As private standards are unequal in terms of supported practices and quality criteria, CRCF is expected to bring harmonization of carbon framing practices and equality between farmers all over the EU.
- The CRCF must take into account local natural conditions. Beside local data, local expertise from farmers need to be considered, in particular for baseline definition.
- Certification alone doesn't work. There is a need for strong support from farm advisors and agricultural development stakeholders.
- Example of combination of overarching standards with private and public schemes already exists.
- Many stakeholders are ready to develop carbon farming projects and are worried that a fully centralized framework at the EU level (including the design of methodologies), will take too long to be operational. To save time, EU methodologies can build on best practice and take advantage of feedback from existing standards. Choices of governance level should consider timing issues in order be able to address the climate emergency.
- A tension exists between the need for European harmonization on the one hand and the need to stay adapted to local contexts and specificities. A good balance must be found to meet these two expectations: general guidelines which would set minimum requirements, while allowing regional specificities would be seen as ideal.

BOS11: An effective policy mix for an environment conducive to carbon farming

Organiser: Mathieu Mal, European Environmental Bureau (EEB), Belgium

The large-scale uptake of carbon farming in the EU will require significant changes in practices and investment by land managers, which must be supported by a conducive policy environment and appropriate economic signals. The upcoming Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) and the CAP are obvious regulatory options, but other EU Policies have the potential to play an important role too.

This session aimed to bring together key stakeholders to explore how the CRCF will interact with other policy priorities and instruments within the EU, such as mandatory requirements, financial incentives for carbon farming, and climate targets. Our objective was to 1) identify relevant policies; 2) identify synergies and conflicts; and 3) envisage what the implementation of carbon farming could look like in the next decades.

ities and instruments within the EU, such as mandatory requirements, financial incentives for carbon farming, and climate targets. Our objective was to 1) identify relevant policies; 2) identify synergies and conflicts; and 3) envisage what the implementation of carbon farming could look like in the next decades.

The main conclusions and recommendations from this BOS were the following:

- The Carbon Removal Certification Framework, the EU's new policy for regulating and incentivizing carbon farming, is one of many elements in the carbon farming policy mix. It will need to be integrated well with other policies in order to ensure the integrity and effect of the intended climate and environmental outcomes. This includes building on the monitoring methodologies set out in the Forest and Soil Monitoring Laws, preventing misleading claims through the Green Claims and Empowering Consumers Directives, and ensuring the EU's climate architecture leaves no possibility of double counting (including double claiming) of climate impact in- and outside of the EU.
- Integrity when it comes to climate and environment means that an instrument should not allow for permanent emissions to be compensated with temporary and vulnerable removals or for emission reduction and removal activities with negative consequences for ecosystems. Furthermore, removals of all kinds should be complementary to and not a substitute for emission reductions. These principles should be safeguarded with care, especially in the case of building carbon farming incentives through market-based mechanisms, such as Voluntary Carbon Markets or Emissions Trading Schemes where emission mitigation deterrence is a risk. Especially as reducing residual emissions will likely become increasingly expensive over time, offsetting through removals will become attractive.
- There is a need for a guiding long-term vision for system change in the land sector to reduce its current negative impacts and ensure it becomes resilient for the future. This change cannot be limited to the implementation of individual practices and technologies that narrowly focus on a single metric.
- The Common Agricultural Policy budget is not unlimited and is expected to deliver on multiple important objectives. As such, additional sources of funding for a sustainable transition in the agriculture sector are to be explored. Nevertheless, there is room for improvement in the way current CAP budgets are used to provide climate and environmental benefits. The development of new instruments should not distract from needed reforms away from harmful subsidies and unlocking the full potential of existing public funds.
- MRV technology is developing fast and may be able to fully support result-based schemes in the future. Policy must integrate these developments, but as long as the technology and methodology do not guarantee high precision and robustness, there should be caution not to over rely on methods with large uncertainties as a basis for financial incentives. Uncertainty, to some extent inherent to the land sector, will need to be factored in and addressed appropriately.

- A hybrid activity-result approach may be able to harness the strengths and avoid the pitfalls of both individual setups, allowing for rewards based on climate and environmental integrity to incentivize quality implementation of practices.
- Increased clarity around the use case of carbon farming units is necessary in order to establish adequate methodologies and requirements, as well as to enable investments and to ensure the intended climate effect is obtained.
- Co-development of frameworks with stakeholders is the best way to ensure adoption and success rates. Deployment needs to be accompanied by adequate technical support.

Communications, dissemination and visibility

To maximise participation, a communications campaign for the event was designed and implemented in the run-up to, during and immediately after the summit. This included:

- A specific website: <https://www.carbonfarmingsummit.eu>
- A mobile digital communication tool for summit participants (developed with the App Eventee) facilitating networking and planning for participation
- Digital campaigns (newsletters, social media, website)
- Media and press releases send-out to over 800 journalists focusing on agriculture
- Promotion on third-party websites

A set of promotional branded and graphic cards were developed to support communications and marketing efforts and to effectively communicate essential information regarding event registration, the call for scientific submissions, online event details, and keynote speakers. The visuals were shared via Credible's online LinkedIn platform, as well as on the websites of the project's consortium partners.

Figure 8: Snapshot of promotional and keynote speaker cards to attract participants to the event

Press Release & On-Site Comms

One month prior to the event, a press release was disseminated to over 800 journalists across Europe writing on the topic of agriculture and carbon farming with the objective of piquing the interest of journalists on the topic of carbon farming³. As a result of this effort, several media mentions were secured in addition to our third-party network dissemination, amplifying the event's visibility and contributing to the broader discourse on sustainable agriculture practices.

Throughout the duration of the event communication efforts were multifaceted and served two primary objectives:

- Particular attention was dedicated to ensuring that all participants had seamless access to essential information throughout the three-day summit. Through curated materials and visually appealing presentations, we strived to provide attendees with comprehensive details about the schedule, session topics, and logistical arrangements. The main output for this was the design of a summit guide, made available to all attendee through download (for increased sustainability).
- Our communication strategy aimed to disseminate real-time updates and key findings to broader our stakeholder networks. Leveraging various communication channels, including social media platforms and live streaming sessions, we facilitated the immediate transmission of advancements and key messages emerging from the summit. This proactive approach not only fostered transparency and inclusivity but also ensured that stakeholders worldwide remained informed and engaged with the impactful discussions and outcomes of the event.

Figure 9: L: Poster in the summit venue inviting attendees to download the booklet, to reduce printing and contribute to the event's low carbon footprint. R: A roll-up banner for branding at the venue

³ <https://www.climate-kic.org/press-releases/transforming-agriculture-inaugural-eu-carbon-farming-summit-breaks-ground-for-climate-resilient-practices/>

Social Media

Social media platforms were leveraged to bolster awareness and engagement both in the pre-event phase and during the summit itself. To achieve this, we regularly posted content through the summit in various formats (video interviews, photos, announcements, summary and key findings). The existing Credible LinkedIn page was the main channel for dissemination, and we promoted the use of the hashtag #CarbonFarmingSummit to systematically track and organise related mentions across the platform.

Figure 10: Snapshots of social media posts during the event

Total metrics for the whole Summit can be broken down as follows:

- 1,810 users viewed the EU Carbon Farming Summit website during the week the Summit was held.
- 400+ new followers on Credible's LinkedIn (from 644 before the summit to 1076 post summit)
- 29,481 impressions on LinkedIn over 3 months from December to March
- 815 reactions (up **275.6%**)
- 26 comments (up **85.7%**)
- 41 reposts (up **78.3%**)
- 16 web and media mentions
- 36 post-summit (during and 2 weeks after) sign-ups to the Credible newsletter

Lessons learned

For the future Summits

There is clearly great demand for discussions and debates around carbon farming and the implementation of the CRCF in particular. Crucially, the high interest from consultancy firms offering products or services related to agriculture and forestry⁴ indicates that these stakeholders are keen to engage with the CRCF process to gather greater clarity and information about the framework and related policies and how they might influence their work. Moreover, engaging with the Europe-wide carbon farming research community and learning more about the latest scientific knowledge proved to be a major draw for many of the participants from this stakeholder group.

Although it was positive to see interest and high turnout in the focus group discussions (60-75 participants per session) the time was too short for deepening the conversations, and for capturing and considering the variety of experiences across the represented countries and stakeholders. It may be more suitable to limit participation in the breakout sessions or open the space for others to create other related side events/sessions alongside the formal ones from the Credible project. Moreover, the wealth of content and information, while highly positive and encouraging, needed sufficient time to be synthesised and turned into key insights or action points for future summits.

Participation in the summit from the quadruple helix was relatively broad and there was strong involvement from the scientific and research community. There was less visible participation by land managers and practitioners (or their representatives). Although two focus groups invited farmers as speakers, many of the participants indicated in their feedback that they would have liked to see more active participation and discussions involving land managers and practitioners⁵ to get a better understanding of the reality on the ground. There is therefore an express interest and opportunity in future summits to hear from those who practice or are transitioning towards carbon farming. This is a concrete objective for future summits, as participation is gradually widened.

⁴ For example, soil analyses, land use practices, tools/resources for MRV, carbon project development.

⁵ The Summit ended with a survey asking in-person and online participants "is there anything we could improve for next year?". Almost 20% of all replies (N=61) said that the summit should have/involve more farmers, foresters or their support organisations.

Figure 11: Panellists during a plenary discussion

On the contents

A clear definition of Carbon Farming should be adopted to broaden its, often restricted, focus on a business model or a way to reward land users who store carbon or avoid emissions. A definition like “Carbon Farming is a whole farm approach to optimizing carbon capture on working landscapes by implementing practices that are known to improve the rate at which CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere and stored in plant material and/or soil organic matter” could be proposed.

The EU level and action is perceived as essential to create trust in Carbon Farming in the current context where a lot of approaches and methodologies co-exist and generate confusion. There is however an important tension to manage between the EU and the local level. While EU generates trust, it should still accommodate flexibility to account for the specificity of the local level. The farming context differs a lot and farmers need to be given the possibility to choose how they approach carbon farming.

Carbon Farming needs to remain in essence a holistic approach of soil and entire farming system regeneration. The co-benefits in terms of biodiversity (from soil to landscape), water, fertility, resilience are as essential as the carbon sequestration in soils.

Carbon Farming does not address only carbon removals from the atmosphere, it is also a key to farm resilience. Assessing productivity narrowly in the short term (one field, one crop, one year) is less and less relevant. Longer term, holistic approaches to productivity need to be adopted and promoted and embedded in the policies and in the mindsets (for instance in the debates on food security or sovereignty).

Many of the conversations and presentations of this first Summit touched on Carbon Farming within agricultural production systems, although there are clearly other land use types which the CRCF is considering (forests, peatlands, wetlands, for example). Future summits will need to broaden the discussions to different land use types and the challenges they face in developing harmonised, robust and credible carbon farming frameworks.

Appendices

Appendix 1: 1st Carbon Farming Summit digital agenda

DAY 2
Wednesday 6th of March, 2024

8:30 Registration open.

9:00 Welcome and introduction to the Summit from the Credible project team.

9:20 Opening keynote speech: the Carbon Removal Certification Framework. Christian Holzleitner (European Commission, [see short bio](#)).

Christian Holzleitner, the Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals at the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action, shapes EU and international climate policies. With a background in economics and a Ph.D. from the University of Linz, he brings extensive expertise, having previously worked on finance for innovation and land use.

9:40 Keynote speech. Carbon farming as an act of transformation. Speaker: Willem Ferwerda, ([see short bio](#)).

Specialized in ecosystems, biodiversity, agriculture, and forestry he focuses on mainstreaming ecology in governments, business, and farmers' agendas. Former IUCN director. Founded Commonland in 2023, developed a landscape restoration framework bringing farmers, business, nature organisations, governments, and investors together. Now active in 23 countries.

10:00 Plenary presentations from 4 related Focus Groups on agronomic practices (10' each):

- Helping farmers to identify the most suitable carbon farming practices.
- Assessing the economic impact of the co-benefits of increasing soil organic matter.
- Carbon farming that safeguards food security and biodiversity.
- Regional living labs in support of carbon farming.

10:40 Panel discussion between the presenters + Q&A with the audience.

11:10-11:40 Coffee break.

11:40-13:40 Breakout sessions 1-4.

Breakout session 1: Helping farmers to identify the most suitable carbon farming practices.

Sparse scientific literature and field-level complexities are hindering the collection of robust evidence on which practices can have a higher impact in terms of climate mitigation. In this session, participants will contribute to foster a scientific consensus on which practices should be prioritised in the EU. In parallel, the group will fine-tune a visually appealing fact sheet focused on carbon farming, and that could complement the EIP-AGRI practice abstract. Our intention is to propose a farmer-oriented, practice description framework, enabling land managers to take informed decisions toward sustainable soil management.

Breakout session 2: How to measure the economic returns linked to the co-benefits of increasing soil organic matter.

For every ton of carbon sequestered in the soil there is almost 2 tons of soil organic matter (SOM) that are built-up. SOM supports the farm's profitability through various co-benefits, including storing water, replacing fertilizers, increasing soil workability and reducing fuel consumption. Providing clear economic data on these co-benefits can help farmers to assess the return of investment for the adoption of carbon farming. In this session we will craft a blueprint for a common accounting approach that speaks the language of carbon farmers.

Breakout session 3: Carbon farming that safeguards food security and biodiversity.

Focusing on soil carbon sequestration might cause unintended consequences, and there is a lively debate on its dynamic interactions with biodiversity and food security. This session will explore these nuanced relationships and contribute to evidence-based insights. Our intention is to draft a conceptual map highlighting synergies and potential conflicts in the adoption of carbon farming in different pedoclimatic regions. Outputs from this conversation will help shape policy recommendations for sustainable scale up of practices.

Breakout session 4: Developing a fit-for-region approach to carbon farming.

The scaleup of sustainable carbon farming, adapted to the underlying agricultural and forestry systems, requires site-specific adaptation and supportive structures, including advisory services, monitoring systems, value chain relationships etc. Collaborations within regional clusters are therefore key to uncover opportunities for scalable solutions in practices, policy, MRV and business models. This session will advance a blueprint for the development of regional schemes that applies the living lab concept for creating synergies and fostering climate actions.

13:40-15:10 Lunch.

15:10 Keynote speech. Modelling and monitoring soil organic carbon in the EU. Speaker: Panos Panagos ([see short bio](#)).

With over 20 years as a senior scientist at JRC, European Commission, he specialises in environmental modelling and policy development. He leads the Soil Health Assessments which contribute to support the agro-environmental policies in the EU. Recognised as one of the main figures at the EU Soil Observatory, he has been honored as one of the most influential scientists globally for 5 years by Web of Science.

15:30 Plenary presentations from 4 related Focus Groups on MRV and data management (10' each):

- Harmonising public and private data for monitoring soil carbon dynamics.
- Proximal sensing and digitalization in carbon farming.
- Earth Observation applications for monitoring carbon removals.
- Using long-term monitoring sites for benchmarking carbon projects.

16:10 Panel discussion between the presenters + Q&A with the audience.

16:40 Coffee

17:10-18:40 Breakout sessions 5-8

Breakout session 5: Harmonising public and private data for monitoring soil carbon dynamics.

A robust system for carbon farming Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) is required to attract investments in this field. Private companies use different approaches in terms of modelling, analytical/estimation methods, and sampling protocols. Furthermore, these data are usually not accounted for in the national reporting, due to the lack of data quality & standardisation, data harmonisation and good practices for data sharing. A EU-wide harmonisation is needed towards a EU-wide system of harmonised national reporting, with JRC (LUCAS) soil monitoring as the central reference. This session gives an opportunity to present experiences on the topic of transnational data harmonisation systems.

Breakout session 6: Proximal sensing and digitalization in carbon farming.

The continuous development of digital technologies brings interesting opportunities for carbon farming, but also challenges related to protocols standardisation and data harmonisation. This session will give particular attention to proximal sensing and related digital monitoring techniques where near surface or contact sensors are used to capture soil properties. However, the water ecosystem of digital technologies for MRV systems will also be explored to uncover the challenges and barriers to their interactions, including digital farmbooks, IoT, drones, digital soil mapping, artificial intelligence and FAIR principles.

DAY 3

Thursday 7th of March, 2024

9:00 Keynote speech. robust methodologies for Carbon Farming. **Edouard Lanckriet** (Head of Low Carbon Agriculture Division at Agrosolutions, [see short bio](#)).

Pioneering the agricultural transition, he leads +45 expert agronomists accelerate the low-carbon shift. He created digital tools to measure and enhance environmental performance in agriculture, advising decision-makers on strategic transformations. Central to climate and environmental challenges, our innovations turn regulatory changes into economic opportunities, shaping sustainable agricultural futures.

9:20 Keynote speech: the role of the EU in carbon pricing and scheme validation. **Valeria Forlin** (European Commission, [see short bio](#)).

Working in DG Climate and Carbon Removals, she is specialized in the land sector's pivotal role in combating climate change. Valeria Forlin focuses on reducing agricultural emissions, enhancing carbon sinks in soils and forests. With a background in environmental economics, she previously contributed to European space policies at UCLouvain and worked extensively in microeconomics, industrial organization, and public economics.

9:40 Plenary presentations from 3 related Focus Groups (10' each):

9. Exploring requirements for the Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria to deliver on sustainability.
10. Pathways towards an harmonised European certification framework.
11. An effective policy mix for a conducive environment.

10:10 Panel discussion between the presenters + Q&A with the audience.

10:40-11:10 Coffee.

11:10-12:40 Breakout sessions 9-11.

Breakout session 9: Minimum standards to ensure that carbon farming delivers sustainability benefits

The proposed EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) establishes four Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria for certification, one of which is sustainability. However, it is not yet determined how this will be operationalised. During this session, participants will share best practices, open issues, and state-of-the-art options. The desired output is a recommendation to the Commission for standards to ensure that sustainability outcomes can be achieved when promoting carbon farming.

Breakout session 10: Europe-wide vs regional certification frameworks: pros and cons.

A centralised European carbon farming certification framework can provide greater clarity for funders, reduce transaction costs and ensure the same level of requirements for everyone. Conversely, a decentralised approach can be better tailored to local circumstances and easier to use for local operators. This session will focus on sharing experiences from stakeholders involved in international, national, and local certification frameworks, to reveal the strengths and weaknesses of the different scales and predict potential interaction of overlapping schemes at different levels.

Breakout session 11: An effective policy mix for an environment conducive to carbon farming.

The large-scale uptake of carbon farming in the EU will require significant changes in practices and investment by land managers, which must be supported by a conducive policy environment and appropriate economic signals. The upcoming CSF and the CAP are obvious regulatory options, but other EU Policies have the potential to play an important role too. This session aims to bring together key stakeholders to explore how the CRCF will interact with other policy priorities and instruments within the EU, such as mandatory requirements, financial incentives for carbon farming, and climate targets.

12:40-13:50 2nd Engagement session with poster display and catering.

13:50-14:15 Summit closing speech: bridging farmer needs to policy and market options. **Giulia Stellari** (Director at Fall Line Capital, [see short bio](#)).

With her experience in sustainable farmland management, she spearheads global sustainable procurement programs, impacting farms in +30 countries. Giulia's expertise includes digital agriculture strategy, supplier GHG reduction, and renewable electricity commitments. With a Ph.D. in Plant Molecular Biology, she also founded AgProveer, a farmer-centric technology company. Serving on the Cool Farm Alliance board, Giulia drives GHG emission reduction initiatives in agriculture.

Breakout session 7: Earth Observation applications for monitoring carbon removals.

Satellite-derived data from public or privately available missions and infrastructures can play an important role in supporting carbon removal certification methodologies. This information is critical in determining the effectiveness of carbon removal efforts and can help guide future strategies to improve their efficiency and achieve climate targets. This session will collect and share technical evidence on the role of EO applications in supporting the implementation of the new carbon removals policy approach and portfolio development.

Breakout session 8: Using data from long-term monitoring sites in the context of carbon farming.

MRV systems should be able to access soil carbon data and the connected experimental data and metadata to calibrate and validate models. However, useful data is scattered and seldom accessible. This session will build on the experiences of coordinators of existing networks of long-term monitoring sites (LTM) to come up with a set of guidelines and considerations to set-up and manage LTMs. Besides, attention will be given to make both experimental and metadata findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) so that they can be of use in supporting regional carbon schemes.

18:40 1st Engagement session with poster display and catering.

21:00 Conference dinner in Valencia (place to be confirmed).

Appendix 2: Examples of posters during the Summit

Below are some examples of the posters presented during the summit. Around 45 posters were presented over the three days of the summit. Each poster relates to one or more Focus Group question areas (explored during the Breakout Sessions).

The Living Cropland Initiative from Ukraine: how to be in compliance with the EU carbon removals quality criteria

I.P.Cert (I.P. Carbon[®]) is a Standard Compliance Services provider and project developing company with a strong focus on Ukrainian farming and sustainable practices.

Our company has developed the Program: The "LIVING CROPLAND" Initiative, which is the overarching framework facilitating carbon credit generation by implementation regenerative practices.

The "LIVING CROPLAND" Initiative is a response to the challenges of modern land use, including soil fertility decline and increasing anthropogenic pressure on the climate system. These challenges can be addressed through the following goals:

- Restoring soil fertility through increasing carbon stock and mineral soil pool in the conjunction with GHG reduction;
- Ensuring accumulation of soil moisture;
- The formation conditions for biodiversity store;
- Preserving biodiversity;
- Reducing the use of mineral nitrogen fertilizers and chemical pesticides;
- Creating conditions for the restoration and preservation of soil health on agricultural fields.

In accordance with RDNA3* the **total damage in the agriculture sector amounts to US\$10.3 billion, while losses amount to US\$69.8 billion**; these figures include damage and losses related to destruction of the Kakhovka Dam. The damage includes the partial or complete destruction of storage facilities, fisheries and aquaculture, and perennial crops, as well as the forced slaughter of livestock. It also encompasses the destruction and theft of machinery and equipment and the theft of inputs and outputs. The highest damage values were recorded in Luhanska, Zaporizka, and Khersonska oblasts, collectively representing 65 percent of the total damage.

Our Program places a special emphasis on war-affected farmers, encompassing those who have endured the impact of active artillery, bombardment, or rocket attacks, as well as those who have undergone demining efforts or are dealing with the aftermath of fuel-lubricant explosions. Also, it seeks to extend its benefits to farms that have suffered from the environmental catastrophe at the Kakhovka Dam.

Since the Russian Federation's full scale invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, the war continues to cause civilian casualties and hardship, damage of infrastructure and productive assets, and disruption to the economy.

*The Third Ukraine Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment (RDNA3), period between February 24, 2022, and December 31, 2023, World Bank and others.

Program's Idea: Creation of a firm climate-resilient and recovery infrastructure to foster smooth transition of the Ukrainian agricultural sector to the regenerative climate change resistant practices; improving fertility and resistance of Ukrainian agricultural croplands; reducing GHG emissions; preservation of biodiversity, as well as launch of educational and consultancy programs for Ukrainian small and middle size farmers suffered from the war to ensure their access to the EU GHG emission reductions insetting programs for raising capital for sustainable economic development. The primary **Program's Aim** is to transition approximately **5 mln. ha of cropland in Ukraine to regenerative practices by 2035, potentially removing around 18 mln. tons of CO_{2e}**.

In the same time the promotion of the regenerative climate-neutrality principles for commodity cropping production by the regenerative land management practices across Ukraine with a focus on GHG agricultural reduction and the carbon stock increase in the mineral soil pool is a one of the strong focus to grow the Program. The "LIVING CROPLAND" Initiative also aims to demonstrate that generated under the Program carbon removals comply with the EU Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y certification criteria. We strive to ensure that removals under the Program are correctly quantified, deliver additional climate benefits, strive to store carbon for a long time, prevent carbon leaks, and contribute to sustainability.

website: <https://www.ipcert.net/en>

Contact us
Hlybochytska str. 40-B,
of. 3A
Kyiv 04050
I.P. Cert LLC
hello@ipcert.net

Above: poster presentation from the Living Cropland Initiative in Ukraine by I.P. Cert

Towards Harmonized, Context-Specific MRV Systems in Agriculture

— The MARVIC Approach

Greet Ruyschaert^{1*}, Hui Xu^{1*}

Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 109, 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium

Why context-specific approach?

- Pedo-climatic conditions and farm types
- Scheme type – Purpose
- Data availability & Infrastructure
- Local policy context
- User needs and preferences

MARVIC is developing a framework for the design of **harmonized, context-specific MRV systems** for carbon removals by agricultural activities and working with **29 test cases in 12 different countries** to understand the impact of these different contexts on choices for MRV design.

Our mission is to boost faith in European public and private carbon farming (CF) schemes by developing and testing an MRV Framework that will provide, to any public or private CF scheme developer a standardized approach for designing MRV systems that (i) are in line with the EU **Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) regulation**, (ii) have an optimal trade-off between **costs and accuracy**, (iii) take into account the **local context**, (iv) reduce **administrative burden** and (v) consider risks of **non-permanence**.

Four agricultural LUSTs (Land Use X Soil Types)

- Arable Land
- Grassland
- Agroforestry/Woody Crops
- Managed Peatland

Identify and improve MRV building blocks

WP2 UCSC Smart Data WR

M R V Activities
Development of MRV methodologies
Applying MRV in carbon farming schemes

Test & fine-tune

Arable land Grassland Agroforestry/Woody Crops Managed Peatland

Accuracy Cost

Assess the potential

- Implementing radiative forcing calculations
- Assessment of Climate Change impact
- Validating carbon sequestration maps in test cases

WP4 WR AU Mitigation potential

- Cost effective
- Policy instruments
- User preferences

WP5 UCPH CZU Socio-economical potential

WP3 INRAE FMI Models & operational processing chains (OPCs)

RULES AND GUIDELINES

- Alignment with CRCF
- Baseline
- Additionality
- Leakage
- Non-permanence
- Buffer
- Double counting

WP1 AGROSOLUTIONS ILVO Design & assemble MRV system

MRV FRAMEWORK

- Decision tree-Context
- Guidelines
- Tools

Contact

Coordinator:
Greet Ruyschaert
Greet.Ruyschaert@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Project Manager:
Hui Xu
Hui.Xu@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Funded by the European Union

Above: poster presentation from the Horizon project Marvic on a framework for the design of harmonized context-specific MRV systems

MRV4SOC PROJECT

Harmonization of MRV systems towards an improved Tier 3 approach

Arthur Monhonval¹, Marta Gómez Giménez², Bertrand Guenet³ and Bas van Wesemael⁴ on behalf of the MRV4SOC consortium

Need for an improved and harmonized Tier 3 Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV) approach

Need

- The development of Tier 3 methodologies is encouraged by LULUCF regulations for national greenhouse gas reporting and by the Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) in the context of achieving Climate neutrality in the EU by 2050. In MRV4SOC, we are developing an optimized pathway to bridge the gap between the needs of Carbon market stakeholders and the implementation of current MRV systems.
- One must
 - Define a harmonized framework Tier 3 approaches should comply with.
 - Identify the minimum set of requirements needed to develop scalable, robust, transparent and cost-effective Tier 3 approaches using different models.
 - Constitute the building blocks of a set of policy recommendations for the standardization of a robust, transparent, and cost-effective MRV approach to turn C removals and greenhouse-gas emission reductions into result-based Carbon payments.

Problem Tier 3 frameworks are neither standardised nor validated in many cases.

Solutions

- Test Tier 3 process-based models and develop their use at local/regional scale.
- Harmonize data, methods and results to ensure transparency and robustness.
- Gather remote sensing data sources as alternative to ensure cost-effectiveness of MRV frameworks.

Fig. 1: Demonstration sites and geographical regions investigated in the MRV4SOC project
Fig. 2: Subset of farms from Soil Capital used to assess landscape level around demsites

Fig. 3: Tier-3 MRV barriers and enablers

The way forward for Tier 3 models acceptance and faith

- The proposed Tier 3 methodology for accounting the full C and GHG budget related to C farming relies on validated models and extensive spatial coverage of input data sets on **soil, climate and land management practices**.
- Model inputs** needed for Tier 3 approaches
 - Accurate land use and land management maps or activity data
 - Climate data
 - Precise pedological data (texture, bulk density, pH, ...)
- Tier 3 model guidelines**
 - Independent datasets (calibration and validation)
 - Uncertainty quantification and sensitivity metrics
 - Well-reported data inputs and model implementation
- Data layers** produced by renowned European institutions such as the ESA Copernicus products, JRC-EUSO for soil properties, the EEA and the national paying agencies for the land parcel identification system (LPIS) and Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) products developed for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) **are crucial**.
- Meet the requirements of GHG reporting at both national and farm scales towards an EU framework for carbon removal certification.

Definition and acronyms

Tier: A tier represents a level of methodological complexity. Tier 1 is the basic method, Tier 2 intermediate and Tier 3 the most demanding in terms of complexity and data requirements (IPCC definition).
LULUCF: Land Use and Land Use Change and Forestry
JRC: Joint Research Centre
EUSO: European Union Soil Observatory
EEA: European Environment Agency

References

- [1] World Bank (2021). Assessment of Innovative Technologies and Their Readiness for Remote Sensing-Based Estimation of Forest Carbon Stocks and Dynamics.
[2] Garsia, A., Moinet, A., Vazquez, C., Creamer, R. E., & Moinet, G. Y. K. (2023). The challenge of selecting an appropriate soil organic carbon simulation model: A comprehensive global review and validation assessment. *Global Change Biology*, 29, 5760–5774. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16896>

Affiliations and contact information

¹Soil Capital BELGIUM, Perwez, Belgium
²GMV Aerospace and Defence SA (GMV), Tres Cantos, Spain
³Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Paris, France
⁴Université catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain), Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium
Contact : a.monhonval@soilcapital.com

Above: poster presentation from the Horizon project MRV4SOC on harmonising MRV systems towards an improved Tier 3 approach

Perennial cereal (*Thinopyrum intermedium*) to promote soil carbon sequestration in Mediterranean soils

Jiménez de Santiago, Diana¹; Casadesús, Andrea¹; Vilaplana, Rosa¹; Ponsá Salas, Sergio¹

¹BETA Technological Center - University of Vic – Central University of Catalonia. Vic. Barcelona. Spain.

*Contact e-mail: diana.jimenez@uvic.cat

INTRODUCTION

Moving toward resilient agricultural systems in the Mediterranean region can be crucial to cope with the effects of climate change. Perennial cereals as Kernza® (*Thinopyrum intermedium*) can increase the long-term capacity of agricultural land to capture and store carbon in the soil through the addition of continuous plant debris and deep root systems. In the frame of TRANSITION project, plant roots biomass, soil properties and carbon changes were evaluated in the Kernza® crop under dryland Mediterranean conditions.

Keywords: dryland Mediterranean; perennial cereal; soil organic matter

METHODOLOGY

Location

- Kernza® crop was established in a commercial farm (0.33 ha) in northeast Catalonia, Spain (41°57'N 2°15'E)
- Mediterranean dryland conditions
- Average annual precipitation: 661.3 mm
- Previous crop: winter wheat

Fig.1. Kernza® plot location (red colour)

Crop Establishment

- Kernza® seeds were provided by the Land Institute (USA) in December 2020
- Seeds were sown in mid-February 2021 (22 kg ha⁻¹)
- Crop management was performed according to the Land Institute assessment
- Soil and roots analyses were performed yearly at the first and third harvest periods.

Fig.2. Kernza® plant after two months of sowing

Soil and roots sampling

Sampling	Dates	Depth ¹ (cm)	Points / depth / sampling	Roots depth (cm)
Before sowing	February 2021	00 – 30	6	n.a.
First yield	July 2021	30 – 60	3	00-30
Third yield	July 2023	60 – 90	3	00-30

¹Three sampling depths were performed at each sampling date

Samples and data processing

Root samples were gently cleaned, oven dried, and weighted

Soil samples were carried into the laboratory, air-dried, sieved, and analysed for the following:

- pH
- Electrical conductivity
- Soil organic matter
- Total carbon
- Total nitrogen
- Nitrogen nitrates
- Nitrogen ammonia
- C:N ratio

Fig.3. Kernza® previous harvest (left) and winter wheat (right)

R-studio was used to perform the statistical analyses (normality test, ANOVA, and Tuckey $\alpha=0.05$)

RESULTS

Soil analysis

Soil organic matter content

Total soil carbon

□ Third yield □ First yield ■ Before sowing

Mean values per sampling and depth (bars) and standard deviation (lines). Letters indicate differences among sampling dates for the same soil depth. Levels of statistical significance appear at: *P <0.05, **P <0.01 and ***P <0.001.

Summary table of soil parameters (average values) at each sampling date and depth: pH, Electrical conductivity (EC), nitrogen nitrates (N-NO₃), ammonia nitrogen (N-NH₄⁺), total elemental nitrogen (N), and carbon: nitrogen ratio. Standard deviation in crochets.

Sampling depth (cm)	Date (YYYY/MM)	pH	EC (µS cm ⁻¹)	N-NO ₃ (mg kg ⁻¹)	N-NH ₄ ⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	N [% (g g ⁻¹)]	C:N ratio
00-30	2021/02	7.5 [0.8]	139.2 [21.5]	31.9 [03.3]	4.4 [0.9]	0.28 [0.02]	23.6 [2.7]
	2021/07	8.2 [0.1]	200.2 [18.5]	21.4 [01.4]	5.4 [2.4]	0.23 [0.03]	30.6 [3.8]
	2023/07	8.1 [0.2]	291.4 [13.4]	47.8 [12.2]	4.7 [2.0]	0.22 [0.04]	32.5 [4.9]
30-60	2021/02	7.6 [0.7]	136.6 [28.5]	44.4 [17.9]	2.4 [1.0]	0.17 [0.02]	31.9 [2.7]
	2021/07	8.3 [0.1]	277.4 [20.2]	67.5 [10.9]	1.7 [1.0]	0.11 [0.00]	50.9 [2.7]
	2023/07	8.2 [0.2]	357.6 [206.5]	43.6 [00.4]	1.4 [0.4]	0.13 [0.02]	47.1 [5.8]
60-90	2021/02	7.2 [0.9]	147.8 [22.9]	65.9 [14.4]	1.9 [0.9]	0.14 [0.01]	38.6 [4.9]
	2021/07	8.3 [0.1]	295.4 [03.2]	77.6 [02.3]	0.9 [0.4]	0.09 [0.02]	64.2 [12.7]
	2023/07	8.4 [0.2]	267.1 [72.6]	55.0 [12.3]	0.8 [0.1]	0.09 [0.00]	66.7 [5.4]

RESULTS

Roots biomass

The graph indicates the root biomass per cubic meter of soil at the first and the third sampling year of establishment.

After three years of growth, average root biomass increased up to 7 times, compared with the first year of establishment, despite the variability.

CONCLUSIONS

- Perennial cereal increased significantly the Soil Organic Matter and Soil Carbon in the dept of 0-30 and 30-60 cm depth.
- At 60-90 cm depth, there were no significant differences probably because of the lack of root influence.
- The increase in root biomass would be related to the increase of soil organic matter and soil carbon.
- Kernza® can increase soil carbon up to 60 cm depth three years after its establishment.

REFERENCES

- Climatic data: <https://www.meteo.cat/wpweb/climatologia/ei-clima/climatologia-xema/>
- <https://landinstitute.org/>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Follow up KERNZA® and the TRANSITION project!

<https://www.transition-med.org>
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/transition-project/>
https://twitter.com/Transition_Med

Above: poster presentation on soil carbon sequestration potential of Perennial cereal (*Thinopyrum intermedium*) in Mediterranean soils by University of Vic – Central University of Catalonia & co.

BIOCHAR AS A SYNERGISTIC TOOL FOR FARMERS, SOIL HEALTH AND CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Tommaso Barsali¹, David Casini¹, Francesca Tozzi¹, David Chiaramonti^{1,2}
¹Renewable Energy Consortium for R&D (RE-CORD) Viale J. F. Kennedy, 182, 50038 Scarperia e San Piero (FI), ITALY
²Energy Department DENERG, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Turin, Italy

ABSTRACT

Biochar can represent a useful tool, in combination with other sustainable management practices, to increase yields, contribute to soil health, optimize water and nutrients use efficiency, and sequester carbon, thanks to its long-term carbon persistence in soil. Altogether, even if it should not be considered as a one-size-fit-all silver bullet, it should be considered as a significant input among a portfolio of solutions. However, the adoption of biochar as a carbon farming method for agronomic improvement is very scarce. Beyond the pricing structure which still needs a dedicated policy to be suitable for farmers' economics, this is also due to the lack of awareness on pyrolysis, agronomic difficulties in cooperating as a community for feedstock, pyrolysis and biochar use, and farmers' reluctance to adopting relatively new technologies. To some extent, skepticism of the soil science community also contributes to this low rate of adoption. Biochar can be successfully deployed in a wide range of different situations, especially in sub-acidic/acidic sandy soils, and in marginal land prone to drought. In addition, biochar can be combined with other sustainable management practices, such as co-composting with manure, or agroforestry, as it can be produced from residues (e.g. prunings, hay maintenance) while contributing to increase the survival of small plants; with drought-tolerant species by increasing the water holding capacity of soil; synergizing with beneficial microorganisms inoculation (PGPR, mycorrhiza) who can profit from its high porosity; with precision farming, by minimizing nutrient leaching and optimizing sub-irrigation; with minimum or zero-tillage operations through seed coating.

CARBON FARMING MAIN STRATEGIES

McDonald et al. (2021) have classified carbon farming interventions into five classes. Among all these strategies, increasing the total organic carbon (TOC) by different agronomic practices (e.g., organic amendment, cover cropping, improved crop rotations) is a promising strategy for both climate change mitigation and organic carbon retention (Chiti et al., 2023).

BIOCHAR DEFINITION AND PRODUCTION PROCESS

Biochar, char, pyrochar, bio-coal, charcoal; there are multiple terms for the same product category. All these terms often cause confusion. In general, biochar is defined as a vegetable carbon produced by the carbonization process, but with specific product end-uses. Hagemann and Schmidt distinguished biochar from charcoal in terms of end use: "Biochar is a porous, carbonaceous material that is produced by pyrolysis of plant biomasses and is applied in such a way that the contained carbon remains stored as a long-term C sink or replaces fossil carbon in industrial manufacturing. It is not made to be burnt for energy generation" (Hagemann and Schmidt, 2022).

The EU Regulation 2019/1009 of 5th July 2019 sets the rules for the suitability of the biochar towards the market of fertilising products. The modifications (applied from 16 July 2022) to Annexes II, III and IV of the EU Regulation include the possibility to classify pyrolysis and gasification materials (biochar) as Component Material Category n.14 (CMC 14). CMC 14 can be used alone or combined with other CMCs to constitute a PFC. The Product Function Categories n.3A and n.4, for example, permit to characterize a product as soil improver (PFC 3A) or growing medium (PFC 4).

BIOCHAR INTERACTIONS WITH SOIL

Biochar has a limiting effect, thereby neutralizing acidic soils and enhancing nutrients solubility. Moreover, biochar plays a crucial role in enhancing soil nutrient retention capacity through its unique structural and chemical properties. Polar sites, in particular, increase soil cation exchange capacity (CEC). Bulk density (BD) generally decreases with biochar application due to its porous nature and lower density compared to soil particles. Soil water-holding capacity (AWC) is enhanced upon biochar addition. Its porous structure acts as a moisture reservoir, effectively capturing and storing water during periods of excess rainfall and releasing it gradually during dry spells. However, the effectiveness of biochar in altering soil water retention variables may vary depending on factors such as biochar type, application rate, and soil texture. For instance, biochar - initial - hydrophobicity could limit its impact on soil water retention in sandy soils. Abrol et al. (2016) found that biochar amendment resulted in a significant reduction in soil loss in both non-calcareous heavy sand and calcareous loam soils. Lee et al. (2018) demonstrated that using biochar along with compost significantly reduced runoff during natural rainfall conditions. The porous structure of biochar, characterized by macropores, mesopores, and micropores, offers habitats for diverse soil biota including bacteria and various fungi such as ectomycorrhizal fungi, ericoid mycorrhizal fungi, and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS AND SYNERGIES

The scientific community, practitioners, advisors, farmers and foresters will benefit from more on-the-ground practical examples and evidence on biochar benefits. Farmers should be encouraged to combine biochar with practices already in place, especially in low rainfall and low carbon soils. Solutions to help farmers to enter current and future Carbon markets should be elaborated and CAP and eco-schemes could support market deployment by including biochar in the list of sustainable management practices that can be remunerated per ton of carbon removed (and not per hectare, as it normally happens with CAP), incentivizing proportionally more small-to-medium farmers.

Combining biochar and compost can provide numerous benefits: on the one hand, the C provided by biochar is stable, while the nutrients provided by compost contribute to the life in soil and to the build-up of soil organic matter dynamics. This combination can be made in various ways, the most effective probably being inserting biochar in the compost pile since the beginning of the oxidative phase. The potential advantages of co-composting biochar with other organic materials (e.g. manure, digestate organic agri-food residues etc.) reside in a shorter composting period, a higher degree of humification, an oxidation of the surface hydrophobic group of biochar (ageing), and a lower N loss from the pile. In no-till operations, biochar can be successfully added to soil through seed coating, which can provide multiple potential advantages, e.g. higher seed density and flowability (for small seeds), water retention in the volume directly adherent to the seed, the possibility to use biochar as a fixed bed for inoculation of beneficial microorganisms. Biochar can also contribute by decreasing soil bulk density and increasing the capacity of water infiltration in soil, which can be a drawback of conservation agriculture during the first years of adoption of these practices, depending on the soil type and previous conventional agricultural practices. A variable fraction of these residual biomass could be successfully converted into biochar, with a number of advantages including the reduction of fuel load for spontaneous fires, the reduction of carbon lost as a greenhouse gas emission, and a transformation of the carbon from organic forms, susceptible to oxidation, into fixed carbon. The incorporation of biochar in soil generates a Carbon Removal Credit which, can be remunerated in various Voluntary Carbon Markets certified schemes. Thus, in a business model where foresters and farmers group themselves, to collect the carbon credit generated on the VCMs can return its monetary benefits where its value has been generated.

REFERENCES

- Abrol, V., et al. Biochar effects on soil water infiltration and erosion under seal formation conditions: rainfall simulation experiment. *J Soils Sediments* 16, 2709-2719 (2016).
- Lee et al. In-situ biochar application conserves nutrients while simultaneously mitigating runoff and erosion of an Fe-oxide-enriched tropical soil. *Science of The Total Environment*, 2018.
- Nogueira, V. Mazzaro Miriana, L. Passatore, M. Zacchini, E. Peruzzi, S. Carloni, F. Pietrini, R. Marabottini, T. Chiti, L. Masciacchi, S. Marinari. Biochar soil amendment as carbon farming practice in a Mediterranean environment. *Geoderma Regional*, Volume 33, 2023.
- McDonald, H., Frelich-Larsen, A., Keenleyside, C., L'orant, A., Duin, L., Andersen, S.P., Costa, G., Aubert, G., Hiller, N., 2021. Carbon Farming, Making Agriculture Fit for 2030.
- Guidelines of the European Biochar Certificate - Version 10.3 (updated on 5th April 2023).
- EBC Guidelines for the Certification of Biochar-Based Carbon Sinks - Version 2.1 (2020).
- Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1005/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003, 2022.
- Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 854/2007.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would acknowledge the Italian biochar association Ichar and all the European and international associations which help spread knowledge and awareness in sustainable practices related to biochar.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Tommaso Barsali - Contact: tommaso.barsali@re-cord.org

Above: poster presentation on Biochar as a synergistic tool for farmers, soil health and carbon sequestration, presented by RE-CORD.

CARBON DIOXIDE REMOVAL AND MONITORING REPORTING AND VERIFICATION (MRV) PROTOCOLS DEVELOPMENT IN C-SINK PROJECT

Juan Riaza¹, Ainhoa Rodriguez¹, Cristina Rodriguez¹, Jennire V Nava², S. Cuesta-Lopez², Verónica Asensio³, Gökçen Saglam⁴, Darina Štyriaková⁴, Pamela Diaz⁵, David Gómez⁵
 1 Global Factor (Spain) / 2 FUNDACIÓN ICAMCYL (Spain) / 3 EDAFOTEC SL (Spain) / 4 Ekolive s.r.o. (Slovakia) / 5 PASEK Minerales SA (Spain)

C-SINK will establish the foundations upon which to build a standardized and transparent European CDR market with trustworthy accounting methodologies based on robust Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) pre-standards and policy strategies. Comprehensive scientific assessments will be made of the various CDR approaches, in terms of (a) their potential uptake of CO₂ (or particulate carbon in the case of biochar), and (b) their safety and other impacts over time.

C-SINK selected 7 CDR-Ts in terms of their carbon offset potentials, permanence, environmental-social impacts, costs, as well as their large-scale potential.

- Biological carbon fixation
- Afforestation
- Biochar
- Artificial soil
- Biochar with CCS
- BECCS
- Enhance weathering

C-SINK CDR solutions comprehensive analysis and characterization

Methodologies for monitoring, reporting and verification of CO₂ removal

Legal framework, regulatory barriers, policy recommendations

Social, Environmental and total economic value assessment

Expected Outcomes & Impacts

- 7 CDR technologies with TRILB with their corresponding methodology, and standardization.
- 7 CDR's parametrization, limitations as well as cost estimation, social-environmental impact, and the investigation of ripple effects and scale of deployment for each technology will be done.
- C-SINK will develop methodologies for CDR monitoring and verification testing at lab and field testing, providing comparable data of carbon removal options.
- C-SINK will use industrial scale data to estimate cost from operations of mining companies, biochar companies and technoeconomic engineering in order to compare the different CDR options.
- C-SINK will promote MRV pre-standards for 7 CDR technologies.
- C-SINK will create a new virtual cluster/community called CO₂ Removal Helix for DC&E strategies during and beyond the project.

CO₂ fixation by plants and microorganisms

The CO₂ produced by soil respiration and organic matter decomposition, as well as atmospheric CO₂ captured by plant photosynthesis, can be converted into soil organic carbon (SOC) through various processes. Soil microorganisms, such as heterotrophs and chemoautotrophs, play a crucial role in CO₂ fixation through metabolic pathways that transform inorganic carbon into organic carbon, thus contributing to the formation of a stable carbon reserve in the soil.

Figure 2: Diagram illustrating the carbon cycle in soil ecosystems, depicting the role of biostimulant application, microbial CO₂ fixation pathways, and the interactions between soil respiration, organic matter decomposition, and nutrient cycles in the stabilization of the soil carbon pool.

Table 1. Biostimulant and dosage interaction effects on clay soil chemical properties

Biostimulant and dosage interaction	pH	EC (µscm ⁻¹)	Ca (meq/100g)	Mg (meq/100g)	Na	K	CaCO ₃	OC	OM	N
Control	7.08*	537.53**	44.85*	12.78*	0.48*	0.77*	2.81*	1.55*	2.67*	0.125*
Inorganic fertilizer	6.99*	592.63**	49.04*	14.94*	0.57*	0.78*	3.01*	1.60*	2.75*	0.162**
2.50%ekofertile*	6.96*	555.63**	47.68*	15.43*	0.64*	0.82*	3.15*	1.58*	2.73*	0.142*
5%ekofertile*	6.93*	609.30**	49.99*	15.93*	0.70*	0.85*	3.23*	1.94*	3.34*	0.148**
10%ekofertile*	7.07*	607.60**	53.32*	16.37*	0.82*	0.88*	3.44*	1.97*	3.39*	0.160**
Control	7.08*	537.53**	44.85*	12.78*	0.48*	0.77*	2.81*	1.55*	2.67*	0.125*
Inorganic	6.99*	592.63**	49.04*	14.94*	0.57*	0.78*	3.01*	1.60*	2.75*	0.162**
2.50%microfertile*	7.04*	542.03**	45.95*	15.09*	0.55*	0.83*	2.90*	1.83*	3.15*	0.136*
5%microfertile*	7.03*	564.93**	49.82*	15.51*	0.76*	0.84*	2.93*	1.92*	3.31*	0.147*
10%microfertile*	7.04*	528.60**	51.28*	15.53*	0.77*	0.85*	3.39*	1.95*	3.36*	0.152**

Artificial Soils

Various components were combined to create an artificial soil layer above degraded soil. It features organic waste bio-stabilized material, recycled construction and demolition waste (CDW), biochar, and dunite ranging from 0 to 3 millimeters in size. These elements are utilized in synergy to enhance soil fertility and structure. The process involves the use of biochar, a carbon-rich product obtained from organic matter under high-temperature pyrolysis, and enhanced weathering, a geoengineering technique where silicate or carbonate minerals are dispersed to accelerate CO₂ sequestration from the atmosphere. Together, they contribute to soil restoration and carbon capture, which are crucial for sustainable agriculture and combating climate change.

Construction of artificial soil layers for ecological restoration, showing the integration of biostabilized organic waste, recycled construction and demolition waste (CDW), biochar, and dunite to rehabilitate degraded soil and promote plant growth

Pilot testing plots at Mina David (SPAIN)

CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS

CONTACT INFORMATION:

Dr. Juan Riaza
 R&D Project Manager
 jriaza@globalfactor.com
 Tlf:+34 624142589

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Above: poster presentation on Standardisation of the MRV protocols of carbon farming systems. A case study: C-SINK project, funded by Horizon.

No modelling - Measure-based on regional scientific data - credible and reliable!

CO₂ Farmer by building up humus. Compensation for CO₂ binding in the soil.

humusCO₂mp
sustainable invest

100% TRANSPARENT GOLD STANDARD

We are setting the standards for nature based carbon farming solutions

Participation

We conclude a contract with the farmer for a better future.

Analysis

The Farmers stock is valuable. This we remunerate after checking with a start-up aid.

Humus-structure

Together we increase the humus proportion in the soil.

Control per year

Neutral & independent survey of CO₂ storage as the basis for remuneration.

CO₂ Certificate

One ton CO₂ bonded CO₂ certificate.

Measures to fix CO₂ - Pilot project southern Germany

Measures for CO₂ determination can be selected from five different categories:

- Nature and Landscape**
- Wetlands and Moors**
- Grassland**
- Agriculture**
- Forest**

Individual measures can be selected from the detailed catalog of measures in the program

The compensation is based on the bound CO₂ equivalents, calculated as tons per hectare and year

ONBOARDING FOR OTHER AGRICULTURE AND FOREST PROJECTS POSSIBLE – “PROGRAMME OF ACTIVITIES”

Remuneration per ton of CO₂ determined

No costs and advance payments for the farmer!

- ✓ Carbon farming as an additional economic mainstay
- ✓ CO₂ certification in accordance with the internationally recognized Gold Standard
- ✓ Security through independent & neutral verification concept
- ✓ Documented sustainable management: Climate protection, adaptation to climate change,
- ✓ Increasing and preservation of biodiversity
- ✓ Proof of ESG reporting
- ✓ Improved public image

Improve the Farmers ESG rating tool

Prepared early for upcoming ESG ratings of the bank and customers.

What is our service?

Payment	Trust	Certification	ESG Reporting
Reliable and regular remuneration per ton determined CO ₂ over five years contract term.	Free of charge and regular inspection according to our Gold Standard certified testing concept. No soil sampling and humus analysis.	Certification of the CO ₂ determination according to the highest standards. The Gold Standard gold standard.	We document for you your sustainable actions.

humusCO₂mp
sustainable invest

Driven by a unique team of experts:

Above: poster presentation on humusCO₂mp, a natural solution to increase agriculture and forestry